

Online data analysis for biologists

Wednesday 21 August 2024, 1 - 4 pm AEST

Schedule

Timings are approximate and subject to change.

Time	Topic
1:00 pm AEST 12:30 am ACST 11:00 am AWST	Welcome and housekeeping Connecting to the Galaxy Training Queue
1:10 pm AEST 12:40 pm ACST 11:10 am AWST	Overview of Galaxy Why use Galaxy What we will do today
1:20 pm AEST 12:50 pm ACST 11:20 am AWST	Introduction to the iris dataset Key features of the Galaxy website: Tools, Histories and the Centre Panel Uploading data into Galaxy from your computer or a public website Organising your data using tags Selecting and running tools Exploring the results of your analysis
2:40 pm AEST 2:10 pm ACST 12:40 pm AWST	Q & A
2:50 pm AEST 2:20 pm ACST 12:50 pm AWST	Break
3:00 pm AEST 2:30 pm ACST 1:00 pm AWST	Workflows introduction

3:50 pm AEST 3:20 pm ACST 1:50 pm AWST	Applying Galaxy to other analysis types
3:55 pm AEST 3:25 pm ACST 1:55 pm AWST	Wrap up and feedback survey
4:00 pm AEST 3:30 pm ACST 2:00 pm AWST	End of workshop